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GENOMIC RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN TRAINING AND TESTING SETS AFFECT GENOMIC PREDICTION ACCURACY OF NODAVIRUS RESISTANCE IN GILTHEAD SEA BREAM

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Introduction

Gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) has been reported to be susceptible to a reassortant betanodavirus strain (RGNNV/SJNNV), posing a new threat for sea bream industry (Volpe et al. 2020) and raising the attention to selective breeding as a plausible disease prevention action. Genomic selection might be beneficial for traits, such as disease resistance, characterized by difficult, expensive and time-consuming routine individual phenotyping. Genomic models are trained firstly using a reference population of full- and half-sibs of the future breeding candidates, but, in a long-term view, the prediction of the genetic merit of future breeding candidates should be satisfactory even when the reference population consists of distant relatives of the animals to be predicted. In this sense, the genomic predictive accuracy provided by random k-fold cross-validations might be unrealistic. In this study, we assessed the accuracy of a genomic prediction model for VNN symptomatology pseudo-phenotypes (estimated breeding values, EBV) in gilthead sea bream in three different validation settings: 1) a random cross-validation; 2) a cross-validation based on genomic clustering; 3) a leave-one-family-out (LOFO) validation focused on the parents of the fish subjected to the VNN challenge test.

Materials and methods

The experimental fish were produced at a commercial hatchery in three independent full factorial matings (10 sires × 12 dams; 10 sires × 7 dams; 10 sires × 5 dams). At the age of 19 d post-hatching, 972 larvae were subjected to a challenge test by tank immersion using the RGNNV/SJNNV strain; the symptomatology was recorded as a binary trait. The experimental fish and their parents (22 dams and 28 sires) were genotyped using the Med_Fish SNP array (Peñaloza et al. 2021; 26,591 SNPs after quality check and imputation). The SNP genotypes were used as predictors of EBV for VNN symptomatology by means of a Bayesian Ridge regression (BRR) model. The accuracy of the model was assessed in three different validation settings: 1) a 4-fold random cross-validation; 2) a 4-fold cross-validation based on genomic clustering, where four groups (336, 177, 328 and 133 individuals, respectively) were created using K-means clustering based on genomic relationships to reduce the relatedness between training and testing populations (relatedness between one group and the others: -0.07, -0.06, -0.03, -0.04, respectively), while maximizing the relatedness within each group (genomic relatedness within group: 0.12, 0.24, 0.04, 0.26, respectively); 3) a LOFO validation, where the BRR model was trained on the EBV of

all animals except the offspring of the sire (or dam) used one-at-a-time as an independent test set. The Pearson product-moment correlation (r) between the observed and predicted values was computed as a measure of prediction accuracy for the three validation procedures.

Results

Genomic predictions of EBV for VNN symptomatology showed high accuracy in random cross-validation ($r = 0.90$; Figure 1a). The predictive accuracy decreased when genomic relatedness between training and testing sets were minimized ($r = 0.53$; Figure 1b) and resulted very low in the LOFO procedure ($r = 0.13$; Figure 1c).

Discussion

In gilthead sea bream, the genomic prediction of the EBV as pseudo-phenotypes for VNN symptomatology led to a very high accuracy in a random 4-fold cross-validation setting; however, to obtain a more realistic insight, a 4-fold cross-validation based on genomic clustering and a LOFO validation were developed. The accuracy obtained in the validation procedure based on genomic clustering was lower than that of the random cross-validation, but still satisfactory, suggesting that in a scenario where the reference population consists of distant relatives of the animals to be predicted, the predictive performance of such model would be acceptable. This is of great interest in an applicative context, particularly when considering traits phenotyping difficulties and complexity. Conversely, in the LOFO procedure, the accuracy dropped remarkably (-85.6%), suggesting that the training of the genomic model was based on data of animals weakly related to the target individual. In fact, the parent contribution to offspring was rather unbalanced, with 3 dams out of 22 producing almost 67% of the individuals, and 6 sires out of 28 producing almost 48% of the individuals.

References

Peñaloza, C.; Manousaki, T.; Franch, R.; Tsakogiannis, A.; Sonesson, A.K.; et al. (2021). *Genomics*, 113 (4): 2096-2107. doi: 10.1016/j.ygeno.2021.04.038.

Volpe, E.; Gustinelli, A.; Caffara, M.; Errani, F.; Quaglio, F.; et al. (2020). *Aquaculture*, 523, 735155. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.735155.

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